

Synthetic Control of Quantum Interference by Regulating Charge on a Single Atom in Heteroaromatic Molecular Junctions

Saman Naghibi^{1,#}, Ali K. Ismael^{2,3#}, Andrea Vezzoli^{1,#,*}, Mohsin K. Al-Khaykanee^{2,4,#}, Xijia Zheng¹, Iain M. Grace², Donald Bethell¹, Simon J. Higgins¹, Colin J. Lambert^{2,*}, Richard J. Nichols^{1,*}

1. Department of Chemistry, University of Liverpool, Crown Street, Liverpool L69 7ZD, United Kingdom.
2. Department of Physics, Lancaster University, Lancaster LA1 4YB, United Kingdom.
3. Department of Physics, College of Education for Pure Science, Tikrit University, Tikrit, Iraq 34001.
4. Department of Physics, College of Science, University of Babylon, Iraq 51002.

#: These Authors contributed equally to this work.

*: Corresponding Authors: nichols@liverpool.ac.uk; c.lambert@lancaster.ac.uk; andrea.vezzoli@liverpool.ac.uk

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1. Synthetic Procedures

All reactions were performed in dry solvents (Thermofisher Scientific), in oven-dried glassware. Solvents were dried and stored under activated 3 Å molecular sieves (20% m/v).¹ All reagents (Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company except where otherwise stated) were used without further purification except the following:

- Copper (II) chloride was dried in an oven for 48 hours before use.
- Aniline was distilled from KOH in a short-path apparatus before use.
- Dibenzylideneacetone was prepared by condensation of benzaldehyde and acetone,² and recrystallised from hot ethyl acetate before use.
- Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ was prepared by adding 1 eq. of PdCl₂ (American Elements) to a stirred suspension of dibenzylideneacetone (dba, 3.3 eq), and sodium acetate (8 eq.) in MeOH at 50 °C. After 4 hours of stirring at 40 °C, the resulting suspension was filtered, and the residue was washed with water and acetone. The crude yellow solid was dissolved in hot chloroform and filtered whilst hot. Diethyl ether was slowly added to the solution, which was then allowed to stand at room temperature. Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ precipitated as deep purple needles in 78% yield.³

Proton and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance 400 Ultrashield spectrometer and referenced to internal TMS and the residual solvent peak. High Resolution Mass Spectra (HRMS) was performed by the Liverpool University Analytical Services, using an Agilent QTOF 7200 spectrometer.

The diazacarbazoles used in this study were prepared from the corresponding dibrominated precursor (either 3,3'-dibromo-4,4'-dipyridyl or 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl) by double Buchwald-Hartwig C-N coupling, using Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ as palladium source and a biaryl phosphine ligand, in toluene.⁴ The halogenated dipyridyls were prepared by homocoupling of freshly prepared 3-bromo-4-lithiopyridyl or 4-bromo-3-lithiopyridyl. The preparation of 3,3'-dibromo-4,4'-dipyridyl has been described in our previous publication,⁵ adapted from the original preparation by Durben and Baumgartner.⁶ Reaction pathway can be found in Scheme S1. All compounds gave satisfactory CHN elemental microanalysis (± 0.4 %). With the exception of compound **2M**, which was previously prepared by a significantly less convenient route,⁷ they have not previously been described.

Scheme S1: Synthetic pathway to the compounds in this study. (i) lithium diisopropylamide (1h, -94 °C, THF), CuCl₂ (16 h, RT). (ii) Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃, XPhos, KOtBu, RNH₂ (overnight, 65 - 110 °C, Toluene). (iii) Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃, SPhos, KOtBu, RNH₂ (overnight, 65 - 75 °C, Toluene).

1.1 Preparation of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl

Lithium diisopropylamide (**caution!** 2 M in THF/heptane/ethylbenzene, 50 mmol) was added dropwise to a suspension of 4-bromopyridine hydrochloride (4.86 mL, 25 mmol) in THF (70 mL) at -94 °C (acetone / liq. N₂). The yellow solution was stirred for 1 additional hour at -94 °C, after which time a white solid precipitated. The reaction flask was opened under a gentle stream of Ar and anhydrous CuCl₂ (8.06 g, 60 mmol) was then added. The suspension was allowed to return to RT, and stirring was continued overnight. The volatiles were then removed *in vacuo* and the brown solid was taken up in NH₄OH (25 % in H₂O, 50 mL), NH₄Cl (sat. in H₂O, 40 mL) and H₂O (30 mL). The resulting deep blue solution was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 x 35 mL) and the combined organic phases were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo* to a yellow solid, which was dissolved in diethyl ether (50 mL) and filtered through a plug of silica, eluting with further 50 mL of diethyl ether. After removal of the solvent, the resulting yellow solid was recrystallized from ethanol/hexane to give the title compound as off-white powder (1.05 g, 27 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): 8.49 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 2H), 8.46 (s, 2H), 7.68 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 150.9, 150.5, 134.9, 134.3, 127.8.

1.2 Preparation of 1M

Toluene (20 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 30 minutes before the addition of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl (0.255 g, 0.81 mmol), SPhos (2-Dicyclohexylphosphino-2',6'-dimethoxybiphenyl, 0.1 g, 0.24 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.084 g, 0.08 mmol), KOtBu (0.273 g, 2.43 mmol) and o-anisidine (0.1 g, 0.81 mmol). The resulting suspension was heated to 75 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which

was further washed with 50 mL of MeOH/EtOAc 1/4. Removal of the solvents gave a crude brown solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, MeOH/EtOAc 1/4, R_F = 0.31) to give the target compound as a white crystalline solid (0.138 g, 62 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 9.56 (s, 2H), 8.54 (d, J = 5.5 Hz, 2H), 7.65 (td, J = 8.3, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.57 (dd, J = 7.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.42 (dd, J = 8.3, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (td, J = 7.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 7.17 (d, J = 5.5 Hz, 2H), 3.72 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 155.4, 146.7, 145.3, 143.8, 131.5, 129.4, 122.9, 121.8, 118.2, 113.9, 106.3, 56.2. *m/z* (HRMS, CI⁺, CH₄) 276.1133 [M + H]⁺, C₁₇H₁₄N₃O calc. 276.1137.

1.3 Preparation of 2M

Toluene (30 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 25 minutes before the addition of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl (0.301 g, 0.96 mmol), SPhos (0.117 g, 0.29 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.099 g, 0.095 mmol), KOtBu (0.321 g, 2.86 mmol) and aniline (Acros Organics, 0.089 g, 0.95 mmol). The resulting suspension was heated to 70 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 50 mL of MeOH/EtOAc 1/4. Removal of the solvents gave a crude brown solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, MeOH/EtOAc 1/4, R_F = 0.4) to give the target compound as a white crystalline solid (0.140 g, 60 %), with spectroscopic parameters consistent with the literature.⁷ ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 9.59 (d, J = 0.8 Hz, 2H), 8.58 (d, J = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 7.60 – 7.76 (m, 5H), 7.42 (dd, J = 5.8, 0.8 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 146.9, 144.9, 144.1, 135.3, 130.9, 129.3, 126.9, 118.4, 106.0. *m/z* (HRMS, CI⁺, CH₄) 246.1032 [M + H]⁺, C₁₆H₁₂N₃ calc. 246.1031.

1.4 Preparation of 3M

Toluene (30 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 25 minutes before the addition of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl (0.301 g, 0.96 mmol), SPhos (0.117 g, 0.29 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.1 g, 0.095 mmol) and KOtBu (0.320 g, 2.86 mmol). After further 15 minutes of degassing, *p*-anisidine (0.118 g, 0.95 mmol) was added, and the resulting suspension was heated to 75 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 50 mL of MeOH/EtOAc 1/4. Removal of the solvents gave a crude brown solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, MeOH/EtOAc 1/4, R_F = 0.35) to give the target compound as a grey powder (0.181 g, 68 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 9.64 (s, 2H), 8.62 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 7.65 (dt, J = 8.9, 3.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (dt, J = 8.9, 3.4 Hz, 2H), 3.95 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆):

159.8, 146.8, 145.3, 143.9, 128.5, 127.7, 116.3, 106.0, 105.9, 59.1. m/z (HRMS, CI^+ , CH_4) 276.1140 $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ calc. 276.1137.

1.5 Preparation of 4M

Toluene (20 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 25 minutes before the addition of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl (0.199 g, 0.63 mmol), SPhos (0.79 g, 0.19 mmol), $\text{Pd}_2(\text{dba})_3 \cdot \text{CHCl}_3$ (0.066 g, 0.06 mmol) and KOtBu (0.214 g, 1.89 mmol). After further 15 minutes of degassing, *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (TCI, 0.087 g, 0.63 mmol) was added, and the resulting suspension was heated to 70 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 50 mL of MeOH/EtOAc 1/3. Removal of the solvents gave a crude yellow solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO_2 , MeOH/EtOAc 1/4, $R_F = 0.30$) to give the target compound as a white powder (0.121 g, 66 %). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): 9.56 (s, 2H), 8.55 (d, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.42 (d, $J = 8.8$, 2H), 7.3 (d, $J = 5.7$, 2H), 6.96 (d, $J = 8.8$, 2H), 3.03 (s, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): 150.8, 146.7, 145.5, 143.9, 127.7, 123.1, 118.3, 113.5, 106.0, 40.5. m/z (HRMS, CI^+ , CH_4) 289.1461 $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4$ calc. 289.1453.

1.6 Preparation of 5M

Toluene (27 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 30 minutes before the addition of 4,4'-dibromo-3,3'-dipyridyl (0.373 g, 1.19 mmol), SPhos (0.146 g, 0.36 mmol), $\text{Pd}_2(\text{dba})_3 \cdot \text{CHCl}_3$ (0.123 g, 0.12 mmol), KOtBu (0.399 g, 3.56 mmol) and 4-aminopyridine (0.110 g, 1.17 mmol). The resulting suspension was heated to 70 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 50 mL of a 3% triethylamine solution in MeOH. Removal of the solvents gave a crude dark orange oil. Hot hexane (30 mL) was added to the oil in an ultrasound bath, and the suspension was filtered while hot to give a crude yellow solid, which was further purified by column chromatography (SiO_2 , MeOH/EtOAc 4/1, $R_F = 0.25$). The obtained off-white powder showed traces of 4-aminopyridine (< 5% by NMR), and it was further purified by column chromatography (triethylamine-treated SiO_2 , MeOH, $R_F = 0.45$ on treated TLC plates) to give the target compound as an off-white powder (0.049 g, 17 %). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): 9.63 (s, 2H), 8.91 (d, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 8.63 (d, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 7.83 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H), 7.65 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): 152.4, 147.2, 144.2, 144.0, 121.1, 119.0, 118.8, 106.3. m/z (HRMS, CI^+ , CH_4) 247.0985 $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4$ calc. 247.0984.

1.7 Preparation of 1P

Toluene (15 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 30 minutes before the addition of 3,3'-dibromo-4,4'-dipyridyl (0.401 g, 1.27 mmol), XPhos (2-Dicyclohexylphosphino-2',4',6'-triisopropylbiphenyl, 0.182 g, 0.38 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.131 g, 0.13 mmol), KOtBu (0.428 g, 3.82 mmol) and o-anisidine (0.157 g, 1.27 mmol). The resulting suspension was heated to 70 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 80 mL of CH₂Cl₂/EtOAc 1/1. Removal of the solvents gave a crude orange solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc, R_F = 0.33) to give the target compound as a white powder (0.161 g, 46 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 8.64 (s, 2H), 8.54 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 2H), 8.35 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 2H) 7.61 – 7.71 (m, 2H), 7.43 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 7.26 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 155.2, 140.2, 137.2, 134.8, 131.1, 129.4, 126.7, 133.5, 121.9, 116.5, 113.9, 56.2. *m/z* (HRMS, CI⁺, CH₄) 276.1140. C₁₇H₁₄N₃O calc. 276.1137.

1.8 Preparation of 2P

Toluene (30 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 30 minutes before the addition of 3,3'-dibromo-4,4'-dipyridyl (0.505 g, 1.6 mmol), XPhos (0.228 g, 0.48 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.165 g, 0.16 mmol), KOtBu (0.530 g, 4.8 mmol) and aniline (Acros Organics, 0.15 g, 1.58 mmol). The resulting suspension was heated to 50 °C whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, and it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 100 mL of CH₂Cl₂/EtOAc 1/1. Removal of the solvents gave a crude yellow solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, EtOAc, R_F = 0.35) to give the target compound as a white microcrystalline solid (0.198 g, 50 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): 8.98 (s, 2H), 8.61 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 8.07 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H) 7.53 – 7.71 (m, 5H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 140.3, 137.2, 135.9, 134.6, 130.4, 128.6, 127.1, 126.6, 115.6. *m/z* (HRMS, CI⁺, CH₄) 246.1029. C₁₆H₁₂N₃ calc. 246.1031.

1.9 Preparation of 5P

Toluene (20 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through for 30 minutes before the addition of 3,3'-dibromo-4,4'-dipyridyl (0.512 g, 1.63 mmol), XPhos (0.228 g, 0.48 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃•CHCl₃ (0.166 g, 0.16 mmol), KOtBu (0.530 g, 4.8 mmol) and aniline (0.15 g, 1.60 mmol). The resulting suspension was refluxed whilst stirring overnight under Ar atmosphere. The suspension was then allowed to cool down to RT, it was filtered through a plug of silica, which was further washed with 50 mL of 5 % NEt₃ in EtOAc. Removal of the

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volatiles gave a crude off-white solid which was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, MeOH/EtOAc 1/1, R_F = 0.4) to give the target compound as a white powder (0.057 g, 15 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): 9.14 (s, 2H), 8.95 (dd, J = 4.6, 1.3 Hz, 2H), 8.68 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 8.10 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 7.66 (dd, J = 4.6, 1.6 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): 152.3, 143.9, 141.5, 136.0, 134.3, 128.2, 120.1, 115.8. *m/z* (HRMS, CI⁺, CH₄) 247.0981 [M + H]⁺, C₁₅H₁₁N₄ calc. 247.0984.

2. Details on *STM-BJ* Experiments

The instrument used in the experiment has been described in detail elsewhere.^{8,9} In brief, we used a Keysight 5500 SPM, modified with a home-built 4-channel transimpedance amplifier based on the design proposed by Mészáros *et al.*¹⁰ and a National Instruments NI9215 USB data acquisition board (16-bit, 10 kSa/s acquisition rate). Junctions are formed by repeatedly driving a Au tip (cut from a spool of annealed 99.99+% Au wire, Goodfellow Cambridge Ltd.) into a freshly annealed gold-on-glass sample (Arrandee Metal GmbH) and then withdrawing it at a constant speed of 20 nm/s in a solution of the target molecular wire (1 mM in mesitylene:THF 8:2 v:v). Current is monitored during the process at a constant tip-substrate bias (200 mV in this study), and the conductance is then calculated as $G = I/V$ as a function of the quantum of conductance $G_0 = \frac{2e^2}{h} \cong 77.48 \mu S$. Each indentation-withdrawal cycle results in a conductance vs electrode separation trace, and thousands of these are acquired and compiled into the conductance histograms presented in the main paper. A gaussian fit of the main peak at $G < G_0$ was used to extract the conductance value from the histogram. The same traces are aligned to the rupture of the metallic nanocontact and used to generate 2D conductance – electrode separation density plots (Figure S1 – S8), which show the evolution of conductance as the two electrodes are pulled apart during a *STM-BJ* experiment.

The *meta* compounds **1M** – **5M** feature sloped conductance features in the density plots (Figures S1-S5), but the variations in conductance with the substituents on the pyrrolic N are clear. Sloped regions in the 2D density maps have been found in other quantum interference systems.^{11,12} The proposed explanation was found in a stronger $T(E)$ dependence on energy, combined with small changes in the workfunction arising from the varying electrodes shape and molecule-electrode binding mechanisms sampled in a break-junction experiment.¹¹ The experimental break-off distance of ~3-4 Å (end of the high-count area in the 2D density maps) is consistent with molecular length when accounting for an electrode “snap-back” of approximately 5 Å,¹³ and with previous measurements performed on 3,3'-bipyridine,¹⁴

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Figure S1: 2D density plot for compound 1M. 5158 traces.

Figure S2: 2D density plot for compound 2M. 3898 traces.

Figure S3: 2D density plot for compound 3M. 5155 traces.

Figure S4: 2D density plot for compound **4M**. 5259 traces.

Figure S5: 2D density plot for compound **5M**. 4723 traces.

The density plots for the *para* compounds **1P**, **2P** and **5P** (Figure S6-S8), on the other hand, showed a more plateau-like behaviour, and the bistable conductance behaviour seen with 4,4'-bipyridine¹⁵ is retained in these planarized analogues.

The experimental break-off distance of ~ 5 Å is consistent with measurements performed on 4,4'-bipyridine.^{14,15}

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Figure S6: 2D density plot for compound **1P**. 5384 traces.

Figure S7: 2D density plot for compound **2P**. 4051 traces.

Figure S8: 2D density plot for compound **5P**. 3122 traces.

All values of conductance and relative gaussian fittings are reported in the table below.

Table S1: Conductance values, errors and physical constants for the compounds used in this study. ^a value from the CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics.

Compound	Conductance (G_0)	Log (G / G_0) $\pm \sigma$	pKa of the corresponding anilinium ion ^a
1M	3.23×10^{-5}	-4.72 ± 0.35	4.49
2M	5.62×10^{-5}	-4.25 ± 0.32	4.87
3M	8.31×10^{-5}	-4.08 ± 0.28	5.36
4M	1.58×10^{-4}	-3.8 ± 0.24	6.59
5M	1.95×10^{-4}	-3.71 ± 0.29	9.17
1P	8.31×10^{-4} (H) 3.71×10^{-4} (L)	-3.08 ± 0.21 (H) -3.43 ± 0.37 (L)	4.49
2P	1.00×10^{-3} (H) 4.67×10^{-4} (L)	-3.00 ± 0.18 (H) -3.33 ± 0.35 (L)	4.87
5P	1.02×10^{-3} (H) 5.89×10^{-4} (L)	-2.99 ± 0.23 (H) -3.23 ± 0.29 (L)	9.17

3. Spectroscopic Data

UV-Vis data was acquired on a Perkin Elmer λ 25 spectrometer, in the region 190-500 nm in dry acetonitrile (Sigma-Aldrich spectrophotometric grade), using a 1 cm quartz cell, at room temperature.

Figure S9: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **1M** in dry acetonitrile.

Figure S10: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **2M** in dry acetonitrile.

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Figure S11: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **3M** in dry acetonitrile.

Figure S12: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **4M** in dry acetonitrile.

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Figure S13: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **5M** in dry acetonitrile.

Figure S14: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **1P** in dry acetonitrile.

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Figure S15: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **2P** in dry acetonitrile.

Figure S16: UV-Vis spectrum of compound **5P** in dry acetonitrile.

4. Additional DFT and Transport Calculations

4.1 Optimised DFT Structures of Isolated Molecules

Using the density functional code SIESTA^{16,17} the optimum geometries of the isolated molecules (**1M** – **5M**, **1P**, **2P** and **5P**) were obtained by relaxing the molecules until all forces on the atoms were less than 0.05 eV / Å as shown in Figure S17. A double-zeta plus polarization orbital basis set, norm-conserving pseudopotentials, an energy cutoff of 200 Rydbergs defined the real space grid were used and the local density approximation (LDA) was chosen to be the exchange correlation functional. We also computed results using GGA and found that the resulting transmission functions were comparable with those obtained using LDA.

Figure S17: Fully relaxed isolated molecules. Key: C = grey, H = white, N = blue, O = red, Au = yellow.

4.2 Binding energy of molecules on Au

To calculate the optimum binding distance between pyridyl anchor groups and Au(111) surfaces, we used DFT and the counterpoise method, which removes basis set superposition errors (BSSE). The binding distance d is defined as the distance between the gold surface and the N terminus of the pyridyl group. Here, compound **2P** is defined as entity A and the gold electrode as entity B. The ground state energy of the total system is calculated using SIESTA and is denoted E_{AB}^{AB} . The energy of each entity is then calculated in a fixed basis, which is achieved using ghost atoms in SIESTA. Hence, the energy of the individual **2P** in the presence of the fixed basis is defined as E_A^{AB} and for the gold as E_B^{AB} . The binding energy is then calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Binding Energy} = E_{AB}^{AB} - E_A^{AB} - E_B^{AB} \quad (\text{Equation S1})$$

We then considered the nature of the binding depending on the gold surface structure. We calculated the binding to a Au pyramid on a (111) surface with the nitrogen atom binding at a ‘top’ site and then varied the binding distance d . Figure S18 (left) shows that a value of $d = 2.3 \text{ \AA}$ gives the optimum distance, at approximately 0.5 eV. As expected, the pyridyl anchor group binds favourably to under-coordinated gold atoms.

Figure S18: Example binding energy plot for **2P** (left), with its idealised ad-atom configuration at the Au lead interface (right).

Key: C = grey, H = white, N = blue, Au = yellow.

4.3 Optimised DFT Structures of Compounds in Their Junctions

Using the optimised structures and geometries for the compounds obtained as described in section 4.1 and 4.2 of the SI, we then again employed the SIESTA code to calculate self-consistent optimised geometries, ground state Hamiltonians and overlap matrix elements for each metal-molecule-metal junction. Leads were modelled as 625 atom slabs, terminated with 11-atom Au(111) tips. The optimised structures were then used to compute the transmission curve for each compound. The DFT optimised geometries are shown here, in Figures S19 – S26.

Key: C = grey, H = white, N = blue, O = red, Au = yellow.

Figure S19: Optimised structure of **1M**.

Figure S20: Optimised structure of 2M.

Figure S21: Optimised structure of 3M.

Figure S22: Optimised structure of 4M.

Figure S23: Optimised structure of 5M.

Figure S24: Optimised structure of 1P.

Figure S25: Optimised structure of **2P**.

Figure S26: Optimised Structure of **5P**.

4.4 Electron transfer

It is believed that the pyrrolic N atom for each compound (Figures S19-S26) gains electrons. Using DFT SIESTA code, we calculate the number of electrons transferred to the bridging N atom for **1M** - **5M** compounds by three methods: Mulliken, Voronoi^{18,19} and Hirshfeld charge.^{19,20} Voronoi and Hirshfeld charges are more reliable than Mulliken charges, especially for large basis sets. Table S2 shows number of electrons gained by the bridging N atom for each compound in gas phase (as isolated molecule) and in the molecular junction. Discussion of the calculations follows. The number of electrons gain by the bridging atom varies from one compound to another, depending on the total number of atoms and the type of atoms (see Figures S19-S26).

Table S2: Gain in the number of electrons by the bridging N atom of compounds 1-5, in gas phase and in the junction (numbers in brackets):

Compound	Exp. pKa	Mulliken charge	Voronoi charge	Hirshfeld charge
1M	4.49	0.465 (0.462)	0.034 (0.038)	0.039 (0.042)
2M	4.87	0.468 (0.464)	0.035 (0.039)	0.040 (0.043)
3M	5.36	0.472 (0.468)	0.035 (0.040)	0.041 (0.044)
4M	6.59	0.470 (0.467)	0.035 (0.039)	0.040 (0.044)
5M	9.17	0.473 (0.469)	0.036 (0.041)	0.042 (0.046)

The net electron gain calculated by the three methods was plotted against conductance of **1M** – **5M** (Figure S27a) and the pKa of the corresponding aniline (Figure S27b), and a clear dependence was found. In all cases a positive figure means that the N has gained a fraction of an electron.

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Figure S27: Conductance (a) and pKa of the corresponding amine (b) dependence on the calculated net charge gain (solid circle: junction; hollow circle: gas phase) on the pyrrolic N of compounds **1M** – **5M**, as semilog plot. Grey lines as guide to eyes.

As can be observed in Table S2 and in Figure S27, the changes in net electron gain are only minute ($< 10\%$), but they contribute to a substantial change in the charge transport properties of the molecular junction. The overall results further stress the importance of small changes in the electronic structure of matter at the nanoscale that can be greatly amplified by quantum effects, resulting in large modulations of their physical properties.

4.5 HOMO-LUMO gaps

The calculated and optically measured HOMO-LUMO gaps are listed in Table S3. Theoretical gaps were calculated for isolated molecules and when the compounds are in the junctions, the gap between their HOMO and LUMO transmission resonances are quoted. As shown by the third and fourth columns in Table S3, isolated gaps for compounds **1M** – **5M**, **1P**, **2P** and **5P** are larger than the gaps between the transmission resonances. This is because the latter are shifted by the real part of the self-energy of the contact to the leads, reflecting the fact that the system is more open when contacted to electrodes. To obtain a more accurate HOMO-LUMO gap, we employed a scissor operator (discussed below).

Table S3: Experimental and theoretical HOMO–LUMO gaps in eV.

Compound	E_g (Exp.) ^a	$E_{g, \text{DFT}}$ (Iso.) ^b	$E_{g, \text{DFT}}$ (Au-M-Au) ^c
1M	4.90	3.43	3.30
2M	5.13	3.51	3.30
3M	5.37	3.42	3.30
4M	5.48	3.47	3.30
5M	5.15	3.50	3.30
1P	5.38	3.10	2.90
2P	5.37	3.01	2.85
5P	5.37	2.91	2.70

^a Experimental data: $E_g = 1241.5/\lambda_{\text{ABS}}$. ^b Theoretical HOMO–LUMO gaps for the isolated molecules. ^c Theoretical gaps between HOMO–LUMO transmission resonances in Au|molecule|Au structures.

4.6 Transport Calculations without Scissor Corrections

The transmission coefficient $T(E)$ was calculated for compounds **1M** – **5M** (Figure S28) and **1P**, **2P** and **5P** (Figure S29). In the absence of a scissor operator, the LUMO resonance is predicted to be pinned near the Fermi Level of the electrodes, resulting in the substituent effect on molecular conductance being washed out. As shown in Table S3 there is more than 1 eV of difference in the values of theoretical and optical bandgap, which is consistent with the fact that DFT is known to underestimate its value.^{21,22}

Figure S28: Transmission curves without scissor operator for *meta*-connected compounds **1M** – **5M** (left) and its magnification in the area where the quantum interference feature arises (right).

Figure S29: Transmission curves without scissor operator for para-connected compounds **1P**, **2P** and **5P**.

4.7 Transport Calculations with Scissor Corrections

As mentioned above, DFT underestimates the HOMO-LUMO gap and from Table S3 it is clear that the calculated gaps are less than the optically-measured gaps. As discussed in the main text, to overcome this deficiency a scissor correction^{23–25} is performed, by diagonalizing the molecular sub-matrix of the full Hamiltonian, then shifting the eigenvalues below and above the Fermi energy such that the new HOMO-LUMO gap matches the experimental value of the isolated molecule. Finally, the diagonalized matrix is transformed back to the original basis to obtain the corrected full Hamiltonian.

In addition to the calculations shown in the main text for compounds **1M** – **5M** (Figure 4a), the same transport code and scissor operator was applied to the *para* 2,7-diazacarbazole **1P**, **2P** and **5P**. As can be observed in Figure S30, DFT predicts a much smaller effect on $T(E)$ at the Fermi Level in these compounds, respective to their *meta* analogues, which results in the conductance being independent of the *N*-aryl substituent in pyrrolodipyridine.

Figure S30: Transmission curves with scissor correction for compounds **1P**, **2P** and **5P**.

4.8 Alternative binding geometry in compounds **5M** and **5P**

As discussed in the main paper, compounds **5M** and **5P** have a pyridyl substituent on the pyrrolic N, that can be an alternative electrode-binding site. In order to establish which possible geometry is more likely to be probed during an *STM-BJ* experiment, we performed DFT transport calculations.

Figure S31: Structure (top) and relative transmission curves (bottom) for the junctions of compounds **5M** and **5P** in the two possible binding geometries allowed by the presence of an additional 4-pyridyl moiety (without scissor operator).

As can be observed in Figure S31, in both **5M** and **5P** the higher-conducting geometry is the one where the two electrodes are contacted to the two ends of the pyrrolodipyridine scaffold, and junctions assembled through the "free" (non-cyclized) pyridyl ring result in the low-conductance contributions visible in the conductance histogram for **5M** and **5P** (Figure S32).

Figure S32: Magnification of the conductance histograms for **5M** (left) and **5P** (right) shown in Figure 3b-c of the main text. Low-conductance contributions are visible. Structure and proposed connectivity to the electrodes is presented in the inset.

Similarly, the dimethylamino group in **4M** could potentially work as additional contact to the electrodes. To verify that tertiary amines (and thereby also the central pyrrolic N) cannot act as electrode contacts as the lone pair on the N is not in a favourable steric position, we performed experiments on *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine, which only gave a raised tunnelling signal, but no discernible peak in the conductance histogram. A comparison between *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and molecule **4M** (normalised to the number of scans used to compile the respective histogram) is presented in Figure S33.

Figure S33: Comparison of conductance histograms for **4M** and *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine.

5. ^1H NMR Spectra

Figure S34: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **1M**. Residual solvent peaks: 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H_2O ; 5.76 = CH_2Cl_2

Figure S35: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **2M**. Residual solvent peaks: 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H₂O;

SpinWorks 4: 3M

file: ...sole-Diazacarbazole DMSO-d6 1H\fid exp: <zg30>
transmitter freq.: 400.132801 MHz
time domain size: 65536 points
width: 6393.86 Hz = 15.9793 ppm = 0.097563 Hz/pt
number of scans: 96

freq. of 0 ppm: 400.129976 MHz
processed size: 65536 complex points
LB: 0.300 GF: 0.0000

Figure S36: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **3M**. Residual solvent peaks: 1.25 ppm = petroleum ether; 2.09 ppm = acetone; 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H₂O;

SpinWorks 4: 4M

DMSO-d6
1H 400 MHz

file: ...line-Diazacarbazole DMSO-d6 1H\fid expt: <zg30>
transmitter freq.: 400.132801 MHz
time domain size: 65536 points
width: 6393.86 Hz = 15.9793 ppm = 0.097563 Hz/pt
number of scans: 96

freq. of 0 ppm: 400.130000 MHz
processed size: 65536 complex points
LB: 0.300 GF: 0.0000

Figure S37: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **4M**. Residual solvent peaks: 2.09 ppm = acetone; 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H₂O.

SpinWorks 4: 5M

file: ...idyl-Diazacarbazole DMSO-D6 1H\fid expt: <zg30>
transmitter freq.: 400.132801 MHz
time domain size: 65536 points
width: 6393.86 Hz = 15.9793 ppm = 0.097563 Hz/pt
number of scans: 96

freq. of 0 ppm: 400.130000 MHz
processed size: 65536 complex points
LB: 0.300 GF: 0.0000

Figure S38: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **5M**. Residual solvent peaks: 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H₂O.

SpinWorks 4: 1P

file: ...sole-Diazacarbazole DMSO-d6 1H\fid exp: <zg30>
transmitter freq.: 400.132801 MHz
time domain size: 65536 points
width: 6393.86 Hz = 15.9793 ppm = 0.097563 Hz/pt
number of scans: 96

freq. of 0 ppm: 400.130000 MHz
processed size: 65536 complex points
LB: 0.300 GF: 0.0000

Figure S39: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **1P**. Residual solvent peaks: 2.50 ppm = DMSO; 3.33 ppm = H₂O.

SpinWorks 4: 5P

file: ...ridine-Diazacarbazole CDCl3 1H\fid exp: <zg30>
transmitter freq.: 400.132801 MHz
time domain size: 65536 points
width: 6393.86 Hz = 15.9793 ppm = 0.097563 Hz/pt
number of scans: 96

freq. of 0 ppm: 400.130008 MHz
processed size: 65536 complex points
LB: 0.300 GF: 0.0000

Figure S41: Proton NMR spectrum for compound **5P**. Residual solvent peaks: 0.88 – 1.25 = n-hexane; 1.56 = H₂O; 2.16 = acetone; 5.31 = CH₂Cl₂; 7.26 ppm: CHCl₃

6. References

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